

Impact of Yoga on Psychological Health in Obesity Management: A Comparative Study

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Obesity is a multisystem disease associated with elevated morbidity and mortality and represents a growing global challenge. Yoga, a traditional mind-body practice, has been shown to positively influence physical and psychological health. The present study aimed to examine the association between regular yoga practice and psychological health among obese individuals. A total of 102 adults (BMI ≥ 30 kg/m²), aged 30-60 years, were recruited. Individuals with chronic medical conditions, psychiatric or neurological disorders, recent surgery, or physical disabilities were excluded. Participants practicing yoga for at least six months were categorized as yoga practitioners, while the remaining were classified as non-practitioners. Psychological outcomes were assessed using the Depression Anxiety Stress Scale (DASS-21), Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index (PSQI), Fatigue Severity Scale (FSS), and WHO Quality of Life-BREF (WHOQOL-BREF). Compared to non-practitioners, yoga practitioners demonstrated significantly lower stress, anxiety, depression, and fatigue (all $p < 0.001$), along with better sleep quality ($p < 0.001$) and higher quality of life across physical, psychological, social, and environmental domains ($p \leq 0.004$). Thus, regular yoga practice may contribute to improved psychological well-being and overall quality of life in obese individuals.

Keywords: Obesity, anxiety, sleep quality, quality of life, yoga

Obesity, a multifaceted and complex health condition characterized by the accumulation of excessive body fat, is one of the growing concerns globally, with significant implications for both physical and psychological well-being (Rani & Kohli, 2024). The prevalence of obesity has risen drastically over the past few decades, and it is now considered a pandemic, with over 1.9 billion adults worldwide classified as overweight, including more than 650 million with obesity (Ryan et al., 2021).

Beyond its physiological effects, obesity is often associated with decreased quality of life (Melamed et al., 2024). Obese individuals often face various psychological challenges such as social stigma, discrimination, and prejudice, which can lead to emotional distress, low self-esteem, and social isolation (Yilmaz & Yabancı Ayhan, 2019). Moreover, obesity has also been associated with a higher risk

of mood disorders, such as depression and anxiety, as well as other psychological issues, including poor self-worth and decreased overall well-being (Yilmaz & Yabancı Ayhan, 2019; Ma'ala, 2013).

These effects are often particularly pronounced in certain populations, such as adolescents (Alberga et al., 2012). Multiple studies state that obesity during childhood and adolescence can negatively impact social relationships, leading to bullying, teasing, and exclusion, which can further affect mental health and contribute to the development of long-term psychological problems (Yilmaz & Yabancı Ayhan, 2019; Alberga et al., 2012). Thus, the relationship between obesity and psychological health is complex and multifaceted (Yilmaz & Yabancı Ayhan, 2019; Ma'ala, 2013; Alberga et al., 2012; Cook et al., 2021). Thus, addressing the psychological aspects of obesity is essential for a comprehensive approach to prevention and treatment, ultimately improving overall health and quality of life (Hemmingsson, 2014).

Emerging evidence suggests that modifications in the lifestyle could play a pivotal role in addressing the interplay between obesity and psychological health (Burgess et al., 2017). Treatment strategies generally combine diet, physical activity, and behavior therapy (Cardel et al., 2020). Physical activity or exercise demonstrates a bidirectional relationship with psychological well-being (Kim et al., 2017) promoting both weight management and mental health (Jones & O'Beney, 2004).

Yoga practices play a vital role in addressing obesity and psychological health (Unick et al., 2022). Practice of yoga has been found effective in elevating emotional processes and bodily awareness (Herbert, 2021). The holistic nature of yoga-combining postures, breathwork, and meditation-may contribute to its efficacy (Gupta, 2024; Batrakoulis, 2022).

A large number of evidences states that yoga interventions among adolescents and university students have improvements in emotional regulation and psychological well-being (Na Nongkhai et al., 2021; Barnes, 2016). Portion-controlled diets can help in

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We have no known conflict of interest to disclose.

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attaining short-term weight loss (Kuriyan et al., 2017) whereas sustained physical activity and continued practitioner contact are required for long-term weight control (Montesi et al., 2016). Yoga also improves sleep quality, quality of life (Woodyard, 2011) and reduces stress, anxiety, and depression (Li & Goldsmith, 2012; Broughton, 2016). Additionally, the philosophical underpinnings of yoga emphasizing mind-body interconnectedness may contribute to its effectiveness (Agarwal et al., 2023).

Method

Study Design

The study used a cross-sectional design where yoga practitioners were compared with non-yoga practitioners in a single session. Participants were chosen from the Southern part of India, Kerala. Eligibility criteria included participants with (i) normal health, (ii) minimum 10 years of education and (iii) Body Mass Index ≥ 30 kg/m². Exclusion criteria were: (i) suffering from any other chronic disease, (ii) surgery, (iii) psychiatric problem, (iv) neurological problem and (v) physical disability. Written Informed consent was collected from the participants after explaining the procedure of the study.

Intervention

The yoga practitioners group consisted of practitioners with a minimum of 6 months' yoga experience who were coming to the yoga studio in Trichur, Kerala. They practiced yoga for at least 90 minutes daily, which was a combination of asana, pranayama and meditation for at least 6 months. The non-yoga practitioner group included obese individuals who were residents around the studio and had never practiced yoga

Assessments

Age was measured in years at the time of evaluation. Body weight was measured using the weighing machine. Subjects were asked to remove their footwear while wearing minimal clothing to stand on the scale. Height (in centimetres) was measured by a scale graduated in millimetres. This scale was placed against the wall with neither lifted nor depressed but facing straight ahead. BMI is calculated from the equation, dividing subjects' weight in kilograms by height in meters squared. Respiratory rate was measured with the help of a stopwatch, participants were asked to sit comfortably and the assessor counted the breaths through abdominal movements for one minute. Pulse rate was noted by placing two fingers over the radial artery, which is located on the thumb side of the wrist and assessing the beats per minute.

DASS-21: Psychological health was measured using Depression Anxiety Stress Scale (DASS-21). It is a modified version of 42-item self-reported DASS. It consists of 21 items categorized under 3 negative emotional states - depression, anxiety and stress (Norton, 2007).

The Fatigue Severity Scale (FSS) (Lerdal, 2021) was used to measure fatigue differentiated from clinical despair; it contains nine statements that explore the severity of fatigue symptoms. Scores range between 0 and 63, and higher scores reveal a higher severity of fatigue.

Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index: Sleep quality was assessed by Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index (PSQI), an effective instrument useful for measuring subjective sleep quality and sleep disturbances. Nineteen questions were designed to measure seven aspects of sleep, where a score of zero meant no disturbance in sleep or good sleep quality, whereas higher scores indicated poor or worse sleep quality (Carpenter & Andrykowski, 1998).

Quality of life (QoL): QoL was measured using the WHO quality of life BREF (WHOQOL-BREF), 26 item questionnaires categorized under four domains - physical, psychological, social and environmental.

Data Analysis

Data was analysed for normality with Shapiro-Wilcoxon test and found not normally distributed and hence an unpaired t-test (Mann-Whitney U test) was performed using SPSS version 18.0 to compare the variables between yoga and non-yoga practitioners.

Results

Overall, 102 participants with age ranging between 30 and 60 years (41.25 ± 9.34 years) participated in the study. Out of them, 51 participants were experienced in yoga who were practicing yoga daily for a minimum six months and another 51 were naïve to yoga practice. The study compared various health-related variables between yoga practitioners and non-yoga practitioners (Table 1). No significant differences were found in age and gender distribution between the two groups, with a p-value of 0.715 and 0.767, respectively. Systolic blood pressure was significantly lower in yoga practitioners (122.67 mmHg) compared to non-yoga practitioners (135.73 mmHg), as was diastolic blood pressure (78.35 mmHg vs. 85.18 mmHg) with both p-values being less than 0.001. Educational distribution showed no significant differences overall. Notably, respiratory rate (15.31 vs. 18.25, $p < 0.001$) and Pulse rate (75.82 bpm vs. 84.47 bpm, $p < 0.001$) were significantly lower in yoga practitioners.

Table 1
Demographic Characteristics between Groups

Variables	Yoga practitioners (n=51)	Non-yoga practitioners (n=51)	p
Age, years	41.18 (9.66)	41.33 (9.10)	0.715
Female, n (%)	44 (86.27)	45 (88.23)	0.767
Education, n (%)			
Under graduation	28 (54.90)	21 (41.17)	0.191
Graduation	16 (31.37)	25 (49.01)	
Post-graduation	7 (13.72)	5 (9.80)	
Systolic Blood pressure	122.67 (11.16)	135.73 (7.35)	<0.001
Diastolic Blood pressure	78.35 (9.10)	85.18 (7.36)	<0.001
Respiratory rate, counts/min	15.31 (2.09)	18.25 (2.28)	<0.001
Pulse rate, beats/min	75.82 (2.44)	84.47 (5.51)	<0.001

Data is presented as Mean (SD) for continuous variables and number (%) for categorical variables. Education is categorized as under graduation, graduation and post-graduation. Man Whitney U test

was administered for continuous variables and Chi-square test for categorical variables.

Table 2

Comparison between Yoga and Non-yoga Practitioners on Depression Anxiety Stress Scale-21

Variables	Yoga practitioners	Non-yoga practitioners	U-value	p-value
DASS-21				
Stress	8.47 (1.93)	10.80 (2.05)	588.50	<0.001
Anxiety	8.10 (2.57)	10.61 (2.10)	593.00	<0.001
Depression	8.75 (1.97)	10.57 (1.90)	689.00	<0.001

Data is presented as mean (SD). DASS-Depression, Anxiety, and Stress Scale

Table 3

Comparison between Yoga and Non-yoga Practitioners on FSS and PSQI

Variables	Yoga practitioners	Non-yoga practitioners	U-value	p-value
Fatigue Severity Scale	33.88 (4.73)	40.20 (6.94)	577.50	<0.001
Pittsburg Sleep Quality Index	3.49 (1.82)	6.65 (1.96)	293.00	<0.001

Note. Data is presented as mean (standard deviation)

Table 4

Comparison between Yoga and Non-yoga Practitioners on WHOQOL-BREF Scores

Variables	Yoga practitioners	Non-yoga practitioners	U-value	p-value
WHOQOL-BREF				
Physical Health	21.22 (3.22)	18.8 (3.09)	1905.00	<0.001
Psychological Health	19.18 (4.04)	15.84 (1.78)	2185.00	<0.001
Social Health	10.04 (1.80)	8.47 (2.17)	1796.00	0.001
Environmental Health	21.49 (3.36)	19.37 (2.53)	1726.50	0.004

Note. Data is presented as mean (standard deviation); WHOQOL-World health quality of life.

DASS-21: Yoga practitioners showed low Stress (U-value:588.50; $p<0.001$), Anxiety (U-value:593.00; $p<0.001$), Depression (689.00; $p<0.001$) scores compared to non-yoga practitioners (Table2).

FSS and PSQI: As shown in Table 3, yoga practitioners have shown high sleep quality (U-value:293.00; $p<0.001$) and low Fatigue (U-value:577.50; $p<0.001$) scores compared to non-yoga practitioners.

WHOQOL-BREF: Yoga practitioners also exhibited high quality of life scores (Table 4) in Physical domain (U-value:1905; $p<0.001$), Psychological domain (U-value:2185; $p<0.001$), Social health domain (U-value:1796; $p=0.001$) and Environmental domain (U-value:1726; $p=0.004$)

Discussion

The current study reveals significant differences between yoga practitioners and non-yoga practitioners in various aspects of well-being. Yoga practitioners exhibited notably high sleep quality, as indicated by a $p<0.001$. Additionally, across different domains of quality of life, namely Physical, Psychological, Social health, and Environmental, yoga practitioners demonstrated significantly higher scores, with $p<0.001$, except for the social health domain with a p -value of 0.001. In terms of psychological health, yoga practitioners

reported lower levels of stress, anxiety, depression, and fatigue compared to non-yoga practitioners with $p<0.001$.

Our results align with previous findings that yoga reduces perceived stress (West et al., 2004), anxiety (Saeed et al., 2010), depression (Tekur et al., 2012), and stress-related psychological parameters such as anger (Yoshihara et al., 2014). One of the possible reasons could be elevation in brain neurotransmitter levels like gamma-amino butyric acid that would have helped to treat depression and anxiety (Brown & Gerbarg, 2005). Besides this, lower stress scores in yoga participants would have been attributed to lower cortisol levels (Kumar et al., 2018) which in turn have resulted in the lower depressive symptoms (Bhushan, 1977). As a form of mindful, low-impact exercise, the practices of yoga, such as physical movements and deep breathing techniques, may have had anti-depressant and anxiolytic effects (Trakroo M et al., 2016; Bandyopadhyay, 2024).

High scores in quality of life, quality of sleep and lower fatigue scores indicate that yoga practices are holistic approach to health that addresses both physical and mental well-being. These positive changes could contribute to long-term health benefits and a better overall quality of life for individuals managing obesity. The findings

are comparable to prior studies showing improvements in quality of life (Asiah et al., 2023) and sleep quality (Gupta et al., 2023). Meditation and breathing techniques likely contribute to these improvements (Sampaio et al., 2017).

The study has several strengths, including a clear methodology that ensured the selection of a homogeneous sample of obese individuals. Adequate sample size of 102 participants improves the reliability of the findings by giving sufficient statistical power. The study design of comparing the groups of yoga practitioners with non-yoga practitioners offers clear findings.

The study has several limitations that may impact the interpretation of study findings. Being a comparative study, there is no randomization in assigning participants to the yoga and non-yoga groups, which raises concerns regarding selection bias, that would have also compromised the internal validity of the study and also limited the generalizability of the results. Moreover, self-selection bias may be present as individuals who select to practice yoga would already have better psychological health, potentially leading to an overestimation of the benefits of yoga compared to non-yoga practitioners. Additionally, the study did not consider the lifestyle factors like has diet, other types of physical activity levels, and social support, which could independently influence psychological outcomes and cloud the actual benefits of yoga practice. These limitations collectively underscore the need for cautious interpretation of the study's findings and highlight the need for future research to better understand the impact of yoga on psychological health in obese individuals.

Conclusion

These findings of the study collectively suggest that yoga practices are associated with positive outcomes in the mental health of obese individuals, particularly sleep quality, various domains of quality of life, and psychological well-being. The observed lower levels of stress, anxiety, depression, and fatigue in yoga practitioners compared to non-yoga practitioners underscore the potential benefits of yoga for holistic well-being.

Acknowledgments

We are grateful to all the participants for their kind cooperation in filling questionnaires and also thankful to the members of the yoga studio for their constant support throughout the study.

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Received February 13, 2026

Revision received March 8, 2026

Accepted March 10, 2026